

Authors' Accepted Manuscript (AAM)

From Annual Reports to Real-Time Surveillance: How Saarland Is Enhancing Drinking Water Safety through Digital Interconnectivity

Boris Dominic Rausch & Lara Wagner
Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Women and Health of Saarland

Originally published in: *energie | wasser-praxis*, 76(5), 2025
ISSN 1436-6134, <https://energie-wasser-praxis.de/ausgabe-05-2025>.

DOI of this version on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174>.

This manuscript version is shared on Zenodo with the permission of the original publisher (wvgw Wirtschafts- und Verlagsgesellschaft Gas und Wasser mbH - www.wvgw.de).

Abstract

In early 2025, Saarland deployed a fully digital system for the surveillance of drinking water hygiene. With R23.Ministry, a real-time platform has replaced the former retrospective reporting process by enabling automated data flows between local public health authorities and supervisory oversight.

The article outlines the legal foundations (EU Drinking Water Directive, German Drinking Water Ordinance), the technical architecture, and the key benefits of the system: rather than relying on annual reports, up-to-date laboratory results, incident notifications, and corrective actions are now available in real time. This enhances transparency, accelerates decision-making, and reduces administrative workload.

Case examples highlight the practical advantages of this technical innovation. A forward-looking section explores the broader potential of the platform—for instance, its application in EU bathing water reporting and its integration with SHAPTH.

R23.Ministry thus exemplifies a connected, forward-thinking, and efficient approach to digital transformation in public health governance.

Keywords

drinking water, public health, digital governance, drinking water surveillance, R23.Ministry, real-time data, water supply zone, multi-level governance, SHAPTH

Suggested citation:

Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). *From Annual Reports to Real-Time Surveillance: How Saarland Is Enhancing Drinking Water Safety through Digital Interconnectivity*. Author's accepted manuscript version. Originally published in *energie | wasser-praxis*, 76(5). ISSN 1436-6134. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174>.

From Annual Reports to Real-Time Surveillance

How Saarland Is Enhancing Drinking Water Safety through Digital Interconnectivity

Author's accepted manuscript version (AAM),

published with permission of the journal: *energie | wasser-praxis*, 76(5), 2025. ISSN 1436-6134.

Original article in German available under the same DOI on the Open Access platform Zenodo.

by: Boris Dominic Rausch & Lara Wagner

(Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Women and Health, Saarland)

Saarland is **pioneering a paradigm shift in drinking water surveillance** through the adoption of a fully digital infrastructure. For the first time, the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Women and Health can access all analytical results and **incident notifications in real time**. The new software platform replaces delayed annual reports, disparate spreadsheets, and fragmented email exchanges with a centralised and automated data flow from local health authorities. **This transformation results in more efficient processes**, improved institutional responsiveness, and a significant reduction in administrative burden.

Crisis response at the Merzig-Wadern Public Health Office: Use of digital tools to monitor drinking water supply | Photo: Timo Perius

A contamination event in the Saarpfalz District in late 2024 underscored the urgent need for a digital solution in the domain of drinking water surveillance. Coliform bacteria had entered the water supply network of the university city of Homburg. The source of contamination was quickly identified: snails had infiltrated a high-level reservoir, triggering microbial pollution [1]. The local public health authority responded immediately, coordinated all necessary measures, and closely consulted the Ministry of Health.

Yet official reporting of the incident did not occur until the following year—not due to delays by the health authority, but because the existing reporting system was fundamentally based on retrospective data transmission. Had the incident occurred in January 2024, it would not have appeared in the national drinking water report until September 2025—a delay of 19 months.

This illustrates a structural flaw: the established reporting procedures are designed not for timely, data-driven evaluation, but for retrospective documentation. Moreover, the final publication of the national report only takes place after the collation and validation of datasets from all 16 federal states.

With the introduction of R23.Ministry—developed by Devagency GmbH & Co. KG in Roth (Bavaria)—this delayed reporting practice in Saarland has been replaced by a modern, digitally supported system. For the first time, all relevant information is available in real time, enabling supervisory authorities to access current data throughout the ongoing reporting year.

This is the authors' accepted manuscript of the article originally published as:

Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). *Vom Jahresbericht zur Echtzeitüberwachung: Wie das Saarland seine Trinkwasserqualität mit digitaler Vernetzung effizienter überwacht*. *energie | wasser-praxis*, 76(5). ISSN 1436-6134 (wvbw mbH).

This version is shared via Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174> with permission of the publisher.

Bureaucratic Bottlenecks: Why Drinking Water Data Reaches the EU Years Later

EU-level reporting follows a fixed schedule. Like all German federal states, Saarland must submit its drinking water data for a given reporting year to the federal government by 31 August of the following year.

In Saarland, approximately one million residents depend on safe drinking water. To ensure this, 70 water supply zones are continuously monitored. The scope of regional data collection for the reporting year 2024 is illustrative:

- 2,111 drinking water analyses were conducted.
- 39,895 parameters were tested, offering detailed insight into water quality.
- 92 parametric exceedances were recorded—reflecting a low threshold violation rate.

Although all of this data was collected in 2024, local public health authorities are not required—under the Drinking Water Ordinance—to transmit it to the state level until 30 April 2025. Until recently, this was done via Excel spreadsheets submitted by email. The Ministry of Health then manually consolidated these reports to compile the state submission, due by 31 August 2025. In practice, this means that a sample taken on 2 January 2024 would not appear in the federal report until September 2025—605 days later. After all 16 states have submitted their reports, the national dataset is compiled, validated, and then submitted to the European Commission several months later. By the time the report is published, the data is no longer current [2].

This example highlights a structural reality: reporting occurs across multiple levels of administration, each with distinct requirements for data preparation and validation. The interplay between the EU, federal government, federal states, and municipalities results in systemic reporting delays. The following sections provide a detailed overview of these responsibilities and workflows.

The EU Drinking Water Directive

The European Union has established common quality standards for drinking water through its Drinking Water Directive. Member States are required to compile regular quality reports and submit them to the European Commission [3]. These data are integrated into the *Water Information System for Europe (WISE)*, which aggregates data across the EU to enhance transparency and inform public health policy [4].

National Implementation and Federal Legislation

Germany implements the directive through two key regulatory instruments:

- The Drinking Water Ordinance (TrinkwV), which sets health-related quality standards. It is embedded in the Infection Protection Act (IfSG) and falls under the responsibility of the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).
- The Drinking Water Catchment Ordinance (TrinkwEGV), which focuses on protecting water resources. It is grounded in the Water Resources Act (WHG) and overseen by the Federal Ministry for the Environment (BMUV).

The Supervisory Role of Federal States

In Germany, the federal states implement the Drinking Water Ordinance (TrinkwV) on their own authority. Operational responsibilities are typically delegated to local public health authorities, which are in charge of day-to-day enforcement. This structure gives rise to two key domains of information flow:

- Drinking water reporting, in which data are systematically collected and processed for national and EU-level submission.
- Supervisory oversight, which ensures that local public health authorities act in accordance with legal requirements and fulfil their operational responsibilities appropriately [6].

In many German federal states, supervisory oversight (*Fachaufsicht*) is exercised by an intermediary authority situated between the Ministry of Health and the local public health authorities [5]. In Saarland, however, this responsibility lies directly with the Ministry of Health, with no intermediate level.

The Ministry's role goes well beyond reporting. It includes the continuous communication of relevant events and administrative procedures, targeted consultation [7] and support for local public health authorities, and the assurance that decisions are taken within a clearly defined legal framework [8].

The New System: R23.Ministry

Until recently, information flows in the two key domains—drinking water reporting and supervisory oversight—were managed independently. With the introduction of R23.Ministry, these processes are now integrated into a unified digital system. Parametric exceedances and other notifiable incidents are recorded directly within the

This is the authors' accepted manuscript of the article originally published as:

Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). Vom Jahresbericht zur Echtzeitüberwachung: Wie das Saarland seine Trinkwasserqualität mit digitaler Vernetzung effizienter überwacht. *energie | wasser-praxis*, 76(5). ISSN 1436-6134 (wvgw mbH).

This version is shared via Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174> with permission of the publisher.

platform, along with key details such as the cause of contamination, measures taken, the affected population, and the timeline of the intervention. This information is made available to the Ministry of Health in real time, enabling supervisory oversight without delay. Redundant transmission across separate channels is largely eliminated. Sampling data—including automated resampling workflows following exceedances—are transmitted directly from the local public health authorities. This automation reduces administrative effort, minimises errors, and ensures consistency without duplicate data entry.

Technical Architecture: Central Coordination of Decentralised Entities

Rhineland-Palatinate established an early benchmark in drinking water surveillance with TWISTweb—a forward-looking approach that enables proactive planning by storing sampling schedules and predefined test parameters for the entire reporting year [9]. All planning data and analytical results are centrally stored and made accessible to both local public health authorities and the intermediary supervisory authority (Landesuntersuchungsamt), supporting coordinated and transparent collaboration. This model served as a key source of inspiration for Saarland.

R23.Ministry builds on this concept, but its architecture is based on decentralised databases:

- Local public health authorities use the application R23.Gesundheit [10], which also supports other functions, such as infectious disease surveillance, public medical assessments, and related tasks.
- The Ministry of Health uses R23.Ministry [11], developed specifically for supervisory oversight and drinking water reporting.

This approach deliberately diverges from traditional IT integration. Rather than merging legacy systems, the platform coordinates autonomous, decentralised entities via the web service R23.Community. In doing so, municipal autonomy is preserved.

A key advantage lies in system familiarity: all staff at local public health authorities were already using the R23 environment. No additional application was needed to support water hygiene workflows. The added value of R23.Ministry is therefore realised with minimal effort, as information is transmitted automatically and made available to the Ministry of Health in real time.

The system also facilitates the secure exchange of official documentation, resubmissions, and complete digital case files, greatly enhancing cross-agency collaboration. Certain data transmissions—such as individual case file access or supplementary documentation—are not automated but require explicit user initiation at the local level, following an opt-in principle.

For sensitive data exchanges, such as personal records or internal annotations, IT security is paramount. The system adheres to established industry standards such as OAuth 2.0 and AES-256 encryption, offering a significantly higher level of protection compared to previously used procedures.

Added Value through Real-Time Data and the Elimination of Year-End Workflows

The new system brings about fundamental changes. From as early as 15 January, local public health authorities upload their annual sampling plans—marking the start of the reporting year. This allows for the continuous transfer of data throughout the year, rather than submitting it only at the end of the reporting period. Simultaneously, R23.Ministry continuously accumulates new data. Parametric exceedances and other notifiable events are recorded immediately after they occur and are transmitted automatically by the system.

Real-time data availability eliminates the need for manual consolidation and time-consuming email coordination, thereby significantly reducing delays in reporting. It also enables crisis response teams to access up-to-date data remotely—even during weekends or on-call shifts. As a result, the traditional “year-end reporting burden” is rendered obsolete. More importantly, the system ensures the continuous involvement of all relevant stakeholders—a key factor in optimising workflows across the official drinking water surveillance framework.

Initial Experiences and Practical Applications

Following the successful rollout across Saarland’s local public health authorities in January and February 2025, the system is already demonstrating its practical advantages. The following examples illustrate the added value of real-time access and planning transparency—ranging from routine sampling coordination to rapid responses to parametric exceedances.

This is the authors’ accepted manuscript of the article originally published as:

Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). Vom Jahresbericht zur Echtzeitüberwachung: Wie das Saarland seine Trinkwasserqualität mit digitaler Vernetzung effizienter überwacht. *energie | wasser-praxis*, 76(5). ISSN 1436-6134 (wvgw mbH).

This version is shared via Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174> with permission of the publisher.

Sampling Plans at a Glance

One of the core functionalities is the graphical overview of planned sampling activities, which visualises all upcoming and completed samples for each water supply zone in a calendar-based interface (Fig. 1):

- X-axis: represents the individual months of the current reporting schedule for the selected supply zone.
- Y-axis: lists the sampling points (e.g. elevated reservoirs, booster stations, transfer points).

A colour-coded system provides intuitive insights into the status of each planned sample:

- Grey: sampling periods as scheduled
- Green: completed samples with validated laboratory results
- Yellow: samples for which results are pending
- Light yellow: samples in which mandatory parameters were not assessed

This view provides real-time insights to both the local public health authorities and the Ministry of Health regarding sampling progress and potential deviations. Users can retrieve detailed metadata, such as laboratory findings, parameter sets, or compliance annotations, directly from the platform. Shared access to a centralised and consistent data repository minimises the need for clarifying queries and eliminates the use of auxiliary Excel-based tracking.

Figure 1: Sampling plan overview for a water supply zone in Saarland

Response Mechanisms in the Event of Non-Compliance

In addition to offering a real-time overview of sampling and reporting plans, the system supports swift and coordinated responses in the event of parametric exceedances.

- Non-Compliance Dashboard: A dedicated dashboard presents all instances of non-compliance, along with analytical details and documented measures—statewide and without the need to navigate complex asset structures. The Ministry of Health has direct access (Fig. 2).
- Case Example – Dead Dormouse: The discovery of a dead dormouse in an elevated reservoir underscored the importance of immediate incident response and the structured documentation of corrective actions (Fig. 3).
- Digital Response Log: The operational logbook captures all interventions, communications, and decisions in a comprehensive and traceable manner, ensuring transparency and accountability throughout the response process (Fig. 4).

This is the authors' accepted manuscript of the article originally published as:

Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). *Vom Jahresbericht zur Echtzeitüberwachung: Wie das Saarland seine Trinkwasserqualität mit digitaler Vernetzung effizienter überwacht. [energie | wasser-praxis](#), 76(5)*. ISSN 1436-6134 (wvbw mbH).

This version is shared via Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174> with permission of the publisher.

Figure 2: Quick access to analytical details in the R23 workspace

Figure 3: Quick access to documentation of actions taken by local health authorities

Figure 4: Operations log - Documentation of an incident managed by the crisis intervention team

This is the authors' accepted manuscript of the article originally published as:
 Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). Vom Jahresbericht zur Echtzeitüberwachung: Wie das Saarland seine Trinkwasserqualität mit digitaler Vernetzung effizienter überwacht. *energie | wasser-praxis*, 76(5). ISSN 1436-6134 (wvbw mbH).

This version is shared via Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174> with permission of the publisher.

Thanks to automated data transmission, the Ministry of Health receives all relevant information immediately after it is entered by the local public health authority. Where necessary, supervisory oversight can be complemented by timely expert consultation and support.

Transferability and Challenges

Saarland has implemented a digital, real-time system for drinking water surveillance—positioning itself as a model federal state for future-proof reporting structures. This success was made possible by favourable structural conditions: even prior to the deployment of R23.Ministry, all local public health authorities in Saarland were already operating under a harmonised data standard (R23.Gesundheit). Additionally, supervisory oversight is carried out directly by the Ministry of Health, which enables streamlined administrative coordination. In contrast, other federal states with fragmented software environments and more complex administrative architectures may face significantly greater implementation challenges.

To address such complexities, several states are pursuing interoperability strategies. For example, the Wafa platform (Wasser-Fachanwendung), used in Bavaria and Thuringia, aims to align heterogeneous systems and establish standardised digital procedures [12].

A further consideration is the risk of vendor lock-in—the dependency on a single software provider. The deep integration of R23 across multiple levels of administration could allow its developer, Devagency [13], to attain a dominant market position, potentially restricting the public sector’s negotiating power. To mitigate this, future implementations should prioritise open standards and interoperable interfaces in order to avoid long-term dependencies and preserve strategic flexibility [14].

That said, a strong market position can also drive innovation. Providers embedded in long-term administrative structures are more likely to invest in the evolution, security, and scalability of their platforms. Previous attempts to entirely eliminate proprietary solutions have often inhibited progress and eventually led administrations to revert to established vendors [15].

While R23.Ministry automates the reporting of drinking water findings, the preceding data flow from laboratories is also being modernised. Until recently, laboratories submitted test results via email as XML files, which then had to be manually imported by local public health authorities—a media discontinuity that caused delays. To resolve this, a connection to the *Standardised Interface and Exchange Platform for Drinking Water Hygiene* (SHAPTH) [16] is already in preparation. In future, laboratory data will be transferred seamlessly and directly into R23.Gesundheit. Through this smart integration, SHAPTH and R23.Ministry together enable a fully digital, end-to-end process that delivers measurable progress toward digital excellence in public-sector water quality monitoring.

Conclusion and Outlook

With its new digital infrastructure, Saarland has established a future-oriented system whose potential clearly extends beyond the domain of drinking water surveillance. A key advantage lies in the ongoing update of the state-level drinking water report: rather than relying on end-of-year data consolidation, supervisory oversight now benefits from daily updated datasets and a prospective, dynamic monitoring of planned sampling activities. This significantly enhances transparency and enables early evaluation and timely adjustment of public health measures. At the same time, digital data recording minimises redundancy and eliminates media discontinuities, making administrative processes more efficient and more transparent.

Beyond the scope of drinking water surveillance, R23.Ministry is already being applied to other domains. Since April 2025, the system has supported bathing water surveillance, enabling automated reporting for all EU-designated recreational waters in Saarland. Looking ahead, R23.Ministry may also facilitate the inter-agency exchange of digital case files. With its secure interfaces and encrypted data transmission, the existing infrastructure provides a scalable and sustainable framework—one that lends itself to further applications across the public health sector.

A citizen-facing mobile application for water quality is also under consideration. As a Smart Citizen Service, such an app could make analytical results for drinking water, pool water, and recreational bathing sites more transparent and accessible. While official water quality reports at EU and federal levels are often published years after the data is collected—reducing their relevance—Saarland’s model offers immediate access to real-time data. This could serve as a catalyst for more responsive and transparent environmental reporting, in line with freedom of information principles and consumer protection.

This is the authors’ accepted manuscript of the article originally published as:

Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). *Vom Jahresbericht zur Echtzeitüberwachung: Wie das Saarland seine Trinkwasserqualität mit digitaler Vernetzung effizienter überwacht.* *energie | wasser-praxis*, 76(5). ISSN 1436-6134 (wvbw mbH).

This version is shared via Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174> with permission of the publisher.

With the upcoming integration of SHAPTH, there is now an opportunity to take the next developmental step—in collaboration with the other 15 federal states. Together, they can shape a networked, future-ready administrative landscape, where interoperability and cooperative governance serve as driving forces for digital transformation in public health oversight.

Acknowledgements

This project was funded through the public budget of Saarland and successfully implemented thanks to the dedicated cooperation of the local public health authorities. The authors express their sincere gratitude to all professionals involved for their valuable contributions to the system's conceptualisation and implementation.

Special thanks are extended to Mr Thomas Schubert, Managing Director and Lead Developer at Devagency GmbH & Co. KG, whose innovative vision and technical expertise were instrumental in realising R23.Ministry. His sustained commitment enabled the high-quality execution of the system architecture.

About the Authors

Boris Dominic Rausch is a Policy Advisor for Water Hygiene at the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Women and Health of Saarland. He is responsible for drinking water, pool water, and bathing water hygiene, and oversees the technical and regulatory supervision of local public health authorities. As a Senior Product Owner (PSPO II) and Advanced Scrum Master (PSM III), he leads the conceptual and functional development of R23.Ministry.

Lara Wagner is a Policy Advisor for Public Health and Digital Transformation at the same ministry. She is responsible for implementing the Pact for the Public Health Service, a nationwide capacity-building initiative launched in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. She also coordinates multiple digital transformation projects in close collaboration with local public health authorities.

Contact:

Boris Dominic Rausch (<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6391-8907>)
Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Women and Health of Saarland
Mainzer Str. 34, 66111 Saarbrücken, Germany
Phone: +49 681 501-3264
Email: b.rausch@soziales.saarland.de
Web: www.soziales.saarland.de

Publisher:

wvgw Wirtschafts- und Verlagsgesellschaft Gas und Wasser mbH
Josef-Wirmer-Straße 3, 53123 Bonn, Germany
Phone: +49 228 9191-40
Email: info@wvgw.de
Web: www.wvgw.de

This is the authors' accepted manuscript of the article originally published as:

Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). Vom Jahresbericht zur Echtzeitüberwachung: Wie das Saarland seine Trinkwasserqualität mit digitaler Vernetzung effizienter überwacht. *energie | wasser-praxis*, 76(5). ISSN 1436-6134 (wvgw mbH).

This version is shared via Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174> with permission of the publisher.

References:

- [1] “Aktueller Bericht – Sendung vom 02.12.2024”, Saarländischer Rundfunk, SR Fernsehen, Dec. 2, 2024. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.sr-mediathek.de/index.php?seite=7&id=147599&startvid=3>
- [2] “Report by the Federal Ministry of Health and the Federal Environment Agency to consumers on the quality of water for human consumption (2017–2019)”, Federal Ministry of Health & Federal Environment Agency, Dessau-Roßlau, Germany, Government Report, Apr. 2021. [Online]. Available at: https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/5750/publikationen/2021-04-06_uug_01-2021_trinkwasserqualitaet_0.pdf
- [3] “Drinking Water”, Federal Ministry of Health (BMG). Accessed: Feb. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.bundesgesundheitsministerium.de/service/begriffe-von-a-z/t/trinkwasser.html>
- [4] S.-H. Kleber and R. Busskamp, “WasserBLiCK – a GDI/INSPIRE node of water management administrations in Germany.” [Online]. Available at: https://wasserblick.net/servlet/is/176376/AKG_Koenigslutter_digitaler_tagungsband.pdf?command=downloadContent&filename=AKG_Koenigslutter_digitaler_tagungsband.pdf
- [5] S. Huster and T. Kingreen, Eds., *Handbook of Infection Protection Law*, 2nd ed. Munich: C.H. Beck, 2022.
- [6] C. Gröpl, “General Administrative Law and Administrative Procedure Law”, in *State Law Saarland. Study Book*, 4th ed., C. Gröpl, A. Guckelberger, and J. Wohlfarth, Eds., Baden-Baden: Nomos, 2023, pp. 104–178.
- [7] M. Burgi, *Municipal Law*, 7th ed. Munich: C. H. Beck, 2024.
- [8] A. Sangs and H. Eibenstein, *Infection Protection Act: including Drinking Water Ordinance*. Munich: C.H. Beck, 2022.
- [9] Ministry for Climate Protection, Environment, Energy and Mobility (Mainz), “TWISTweb”. Accessed: Mar. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available at: <https://twist.rlp-umwelt.de/twist/default.htm>
- [10] “R23.Gesundheit”. Accessed: Feb. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available at: <https://r23.technology/gesundheit>
- [11] “R23.Ministerium”. Accessed: Feb. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available at: <https://r23.technology/ministerium>
- [12] Federal Ministry of Health, “Unified Water Application (Wafa) for Bavaria and Thuringia”. Accessed: Mar. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available at: <https://gesundheitsamt-2025.de/projekte/projektvorstellungen/einheitliche-wasser-fachanwendung-wafa-fuer-bayern-und-thueringen>
- [13] “DEVAGENCY”. Accessed: Mar. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available at: <https://devagency.de/>
- [14] B. Stukenberg, “LiMux: Is Open-Source Software an Alternative for Public Administration?”, Diploma Thesis, University of Hamburg, 2007. [Online]. Available at: https://swa.informatik.uni-hamburg.de/files/abschlussarbeiten/Diplomarbeit_LiMux.pdf
- [15] M. Hauck, “Munich: When the Microsoft CEO Interrupted His Ski Holiday”, Sueddeutsche.de. Accessed: Mar. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.sueddeutsche.de/muenchen/muenchen-microsoft-linux-verwaltung-1.5562006>
- [16] Bavarian State Office for Health and Food Safety, “SHAPTH. Interface Harmonization and Exchange Platform for Drinking Water Hygiene. Landing Page”, shapth.info. Accessed: Feb. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available at: <https://shapth.info/>

This is the authors' accepted manuscript of the article originally published as:

Rausch, B. D., & Wagner, L. (2025). *Vom Jahresbericht zur Echtzeitüberwachung: Wie das Saarland seine Trinkwasserqualität mit digitaler Vernetzung effizienter überwacht. energie | wasser-praxis, 76(5)*. ISSN 1436-6134 (wvbw mbH).

This version is shared via Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356174> with permission of the publisher.